

Effective Longitudinal Young's Modulus of Two-Dimensionally Misoriented Short Fiber Composites

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the effective longitudinal Young's modulus of composites containing two-dimensionally misoriented short fibers. The analysis is based upon the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method and the average induced strain approach of Taya, Mura and Chou. The present approach is unique in that it takes into account the interactions among fibers at different orientations. Numerical results are presented to demonstrate the effects of fiber elastic property, aspect ratio, volume fraction and orientation distribution function on composite Young's modulus.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous fiber reinforced composites are attractive not only in their relatively low fabrication cost but also in their versatility in properties. They consist of relatively short, variable length and imperfectly aligned fibers distributed in a continuous matrix material. The orientation of the short fibers depends upon the processing conditions employed and may vary from random to nearly aligned. Thus, it is imperative to take into consideration the effects of the bias in fiber orientation and variation in fiber aspect ratio on composite elastic properties.

The stiffness properties of two-dimensionally random fiber reinforced composite were analyzed first by Cox[1], who treated the general distribution of orientation of the continuous fibers and used the classical lamination analogy: such materials can be modelled as laminated systems composed of layers of unidirectional fiber composites oriented at specific angles with respect to the reference axes. The results by Cox were obtained by summing up the contributions to stiffness for all the fiber orientations. The stiffness value of each orientation was obtained by the tensor transformation of stiffness of the system with aligned fibers parallel to the loading direction. In his analysis for the continuous fiber, the contribution of matrix to the stiffness was neglected. He also discussed the effect of aspect ratio by applying the shear lag theory. Nielsen and Chen[2] made a numerical calculation and obtained the graphical data, and Halpin and Pagano[3] presented their results in terms of the effective properties of an aligned composite. Halpin et al.[4] used one of the realistic distribution patterns of short fibers. Christensen and Waals[5] related their results to the properties of the

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fiber and matrix phase, and Manera[6] proposed the simplified equation.

The above analyses have been based on the classical lamination theory. So the interactions between fibers at different orientations are not considered. Second, they considered the completely random distribution of fibers except Reference[4]. The experimental results[7] indicated that during the molding process most fibers tend to be aligned along the flow direction for the case of high volume fraction of fiber, whereas they are less oriented along the flow direction for the case of low volume fraction of fiber.

In this paper, we consider the effect of the distribution in fiber orientation on the effective Young's modulus, and the interaction among fibers at different orientations is included in the analysis by adopting the average induced strain approach[8,9] and the modified Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method[10]. The present method is based on the analytical model by Takao et al.[11], who formulated for the case of three-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composite system. In other words, we modify the three-dimensional model of Takao et al. into the case of the two-dimensional fiber orientation. In order to verify the analytical model we compare the theoretical results predicted by the present model with the experimental ones reported for glass/epoxy, glass/polystyrene(polystyrene-co-acrylonitrile), glass/epoxy and glass/polyester by Nielsen and Chen[2], Lee[12], Lavengood[13] and Manera[6], respectively. Lee and Manera presented the systematic results.

The formulation based on the average induced strain approach and the modified Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method to the misoriented fiber reinforced composites is described first. Then it is shown that the number of non-vanishing components of the averaged induced strain is reduced to three. The solution procedure to obtain the effective Young's modulus is described. Numerical results of the effective Young's modulus are presented for two types of fiber distribution patterns(uniform and cosine-type) with the parameter of distribution limit α of the fiber orientation angle, together with previous theoretical or experimental studies. The effects of the volume fraction of fiber f , the aspect ratio of fiber l/d , and the fiber-matrix Young's modulus ratio E_f/E_0 on the composite stiffness are discussed.

FORMULATION

The infinite elastic body containing two-dimensionally misoriented short fibers and subjected to the applied stress σ_0 is shown in Fig. 1a. All the fibers are assumed to lie in the x_2 - x_3 plane. The fibers are modelled as ellipsoidal inclusions of the same size. Let the domains of the infinite body and the fibers (inhomogeneity) be denoted by D and Ω , respectively. Hence the domain of the matrix becomes $D-\Omega$. The elastic stiffness tensors of the matrix and fiber are denoted by \tilde{C}_0 and \tilde{C}_f , respectively. The tilde stands for tensorial quantity. Under the applied stress $\tilde{\sigma}_0$ the average of the total stress in the matrix can be given by $\langle \tilde{\sigma} \rangle + \langle \tilde{\sigma}' \rangle$ [14], where

$$\langle \tilde{\sigma} \rangle = \tilde{C}_0 \bar{\tilde{\epsilon}} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\langle \rangle$ denotes the volume average of a quantity and $\bar{\tilde{\epsilon}}$ stands for the average disturbance in strain of the matrix due to the presence of all fibers.

Now, a single fiber is introduced into the composite D . The orientation of this fiber is defined by the angle θ as shown in Fig. 1b. To apply the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method[10] to this single fiber the local coordinate system $x_1'x_2'x_3'$ is also adopted, where the x_3' axis coincides with the fiber axis. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\sigma}' + \tilde{\sigma} &= \tilde{C}_0 (\tilde{\epsilon}' + \bar{\tilde{\epsilon}} + \tilde{\epsilon} - \tilde{\epsilon}^{*'}) \\ &= \tilde{C}_f (\tilde{\epsilon}' + \bar{\tilde{\epsilon}} + \tilde{\epsilon}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\tilde{\epsilon}' = \tilde{\xi} \tilde{\epsilon}^{*'} \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}'$ is the disturbances of stress due to this single fiber, $\tilde{\epsilon}'$ is that of strain due to only this single fiber, $\tilde{\xi}$ is the Eshelby tensor for Ω (see Reference[15]), and $\tilde{\epsilon}^{*'}$ is the eigenstrain(or transformation strain) which has

Fig. 1 The Calculation Model

non-vanishing components in Ω , but becomes zero outside Ω . The prime indicates tensorial quantities referred to the local coordinate system $x_1' x_2' x_3'$. In eq.(2)

$$\sigma_0' = \zeta_0 \epsilon_0' \quad (\text{or } \sigma_0 = \zeta_0 \epsilon_0) \quad (4)$$

Then the stress disturbance σ' in Ω can be obtained from eq.(2).

$$\sigma' = \zeta_0 (\bar{\epsilon}' + \xi \epsilon^{*'} - \epsilon^{*'}) \quad (5)$$

Since the added single fiber can be regarded as any fiber in the composite, eqs. (2) and (5) hold for any inhomogeneity in the matrix. Eq.(2) and the tensor transformation T^{-1} from the global coordinate system $x_1 x_2 x_3$ to the local one $x_1' x_2' x_3'$ yield

$$\epsilon^{*'} = -((\zeta_f - \zeta_0)\xi + \zeta_0)^{-1} (\zeta_f - \zeta_0) T^{-1} (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (6)$$

and

$$\epsilon' - \epsilon^{*'} = -(\xi - I) ((\zeta_f - \zeta_0)\xi + \zeta_0)^{-1} (\zeta_f - \zeta_0) T^{-1} (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (7)$$

The values of $\epsilon_0' - \epsilon^{*'}$ in eq.(7), after being transformed to the global coordinate system of $\bar{x}_1 \bar{x}_2 \bar{x}_3$ with the use of the tensor transformation T , are applied to the following relation

$$\bar{\epsilon} + 1/V_D \int_{\Omega} (\epsilon - \epsilon^{*'}) dV = 0 \quad (8)$$

to obtain

$$\bar{\epsilon} - 1/V_D \int_{\Omega} T (\xi - I) ((\zeta_f - \zeta_0)\xi + \zeta_0)^{-1} (\zeta_f - \zeta_0) T^{-1} dV \cdot (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where V_D denotes the volume of the domain D . In the above derivation it is assumed that ϵ_0 and $\bar{\epsilon}$ are constant on the whole domain. It is shown in Appendix A of Reference[11] that eq.(8) is equivalent to the requirement that the integral of the stress disturbance over the whole domain vanishes, namely, $\int_D \sigma' dV = 0$. Eq.(9) represents in general six linear algebraic equations with the six unknown components of $\bar{\epsilon}$.

Let the number of fibers with misorientation angle between θ and $\theta + d\theta$ be denoted by $\rho(\theta)$, the lower and upper limits on the orientation angle by β and α , respectively, and the volume of the single fiber by v_f . Then eq.(9) is re-written as follows with the use of the relation $dV = v_f \rho(\theta) d\theta$.

$$\bar{\epsilon} = f \left(\int_{\beta}^{\alpha} v_f \rho(\theta) d\theta \right)^{-1} \cdot \int_{\beta}^{\alpha} T G T^{-1} v_f \rho(\theta) d\theta \cdot (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}) \quad (10)$$

where f is the volume fraction of fiber and $G = (\xi - I) \cdot ((\xi_f - \xi_0) \xi + \xi_0)^{-1} (\xi_f - \xi_0)$. We suppose that $\beta = -\alpha$, $\rho(\theta)$ is the even function, and every fiber has the same volume. In this case we can show that

$$F_{ij} = 0 \quad (3 < i \text{ or } 3 < j, i \neq j) \quad (11)$$

where

$$F \left(\equiv [F_{ij}] \right) = - \left(\int_{\alpha}^{\alpha} v_f \rho(\theta) d\theta \right)^{-1} \cdot \int_{\alpha}^{\alpha} T G T^{-1} v_f \rho(\theta) d\theta \quad (12)$$

Applying eqs.(11) and (12) to eq.(10) yields

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + f \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} & F_{13} \\ F_{21} & F_{22} & F_{23} \\ F_{31} & F_{32} & F_{33} \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{11} \\ \bar{e}_{22} \\ \bar{e}_{33} \end{bmatrix} = - f \begin{bmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} & F_{13} \\ F_{21} & F_{22} & F_{23} \\ F_{31} & F_{32} & F_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_{0,11} \\ e_{0,22} \\ e_{0,33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13-a)$$

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + f \begin{bmatrix} F_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & F_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & F_{66} \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{12} \\ \bar{e}_{13} \\ \bar{e}_{23} \end{bmatrix} = - f \begin{bmatrix} F_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & F_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & F_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_{0,12} \\ e_{0,13} \\ e_{0,23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13-b)$$

where

$$\bar{\epsilon} = (\bar{e}_{11}, \bar{e}_{22}, \bar{e}_{33}, \bar{e}_{12}, \bar{e}_{13}, \bar{e}_{23})^t \quad (14)$$

$$\epsilon_0 = (e_{0,11}, e_{0,22}, e_{0,33}, e_{0,12}, e_{0,13}, e_{0,23})^t$$

In eqs.(11) to (14) we use the vector and matrix notation. It should be noted that v_f and the absolute value of $\rho(\theta)$ in eq.(12) have no meaning due to the reduction. We consider here that a stress σ_0 is applied along the x_3 -axis as shown in Fig. 1a. Then $e_{0,12} = e_{0,13} = e_{0,23} = 0$. Thus $\bar{e}_{12} = \bar{e}_{13} = \bar{e}_{23} = 0$ from eq.(13-b). There are only three unknown components: \bar{e}_{11} , \bar{e}_{22} and \bar{e}_{33} .

Furthermore, the equivalency of the strain energies of the composite system [8,9] is expressed by

$$1/2 \xi_0 \xi_c^{-1} \xi_0 = 1/2 \xi_0 \epsilon_0 + 1/2 \cdot 1/V_D \int_{\Omega} \xi_0 \epsilon^* dV \quad (15)$$

where ξ_c is the effective stiffness tensor of the composite to be computed. Then applying $\xi_0 = (0, 0, \sigma_0, 0, 0, 0)^t$ to eq.(15) we can obtain the effective longitudinal Young's modulus E_L of the composite as follows

$$E_L/E_0 = \left(1 + \frac{E_0}{\sigma_0} \frac{1}{V_D} \int_{\Omega} e^*_{33} dV \right)^{-1} \quad (16)$$

where E_0 is the Young's modulus of the matrix and e^*_{33} is the normal eigenstrain along the x_3 -axis.

Inputting solutions of \bar{e}_{11} , \bar{e}_{22} and \bar{e}_{33} into eq.(9) and replacing $\xi - I$ by ξ in eq.(9) lead to the result that the left hand side of eq.(9) becomes $1/V_D \int_{\Omega} e^* dV$. This value is substituted into eq.(16) to obtain the solution of E_L .

RESULT

Results of this analysis is first compared with the experimental data and previous theoretical solution where the fibers are completely random in their orientation within the plate. Fig. 2 shows the theoretical results[5] and the experimental results[6, 12 and 13]: the effective Young's modulus E_L of the glass fiber reinforced composites and both are normalized by the present theoretical ones $E_{L,p}$. In this figure, the experimental results plotted by symbols and the theoretical results by Christensen and Waals given by solid curve are presented as a function of the volume fraction of fiber f . Four kinds of matrices were used in

Fig. 2 The Comparison of Present Results with Other Ones

Table 1 Elastic properties, E_f/E_0 , ν_f , and ν_0 and Aspect Ratio l/d of Composites in Fig. 2

Composite System	Ref.	E_f/E_0	Poisson's Ratio ν_f	ν_0	l/d
G/polystyrene [5,12]		22.34	0.25	0.32	675
G/polystyrene-co-acrylonitrile [12]		19.81	-	0.32	675
G/epoxy [13]		30.0	-	0.42	10^4
G/polyester [6]		32.44	-	0.4	300

the previous studies, where the properties of the matrix and the aspect ratio of fiber used are different from one another. We used the same material properties and aspect ratio as shown in Table 2 to obtain $E_{L,P}$.

In the following figures we demonstrate the effects of fiber density distribution along with E_f/E_0 , l/d , and f on E_L . Mainly the case of short carbon fiber reinforced polyamide 66 is considered and its elastic properties are $E_f/E_0 = 100$, $\nu_f = 0.17$, and $\nu_0 = 0.42$. To demonstrate the effect of E_f/E_0 , two cases are considered: $E_f/E_0 = 30$ and 200 . Two fiber density distributions, uniform $\rho = \rho_0$ and cosine $\rho = \rho_0 \cos(\pi/2 \cdot \theta/\alpha)$ types, are also examined. As stated above, the angle α denotes the range of fiber orientation distribution relative to the x_3 axis or the loading direction. Fig. 3 shows E_L as a function of α in the case of $\rho = \rho_0$ and $f = 0.2$ with the parameter $l/d = 10, 30, 50$ and 1000 (the results beyond $l/d = 50$ practically result in a single curve). The effective moduli are normalized by E_{*x} , the composite effective Young's modulus when all fibers are aligned with the x_3 axis. At $l/d > 30$ the change in E_L/E_{*x} becomes small. The values of E_{*x} are shown in Table 2 for $E_f/E_0 = 30$ and 100 .

Fig. 4 shows the effect of E_f/E_0 on E_L/E_{*x} as a function of α for the case of $\rho = \rho_0$, $l/d = 50$ and $f = 0.2$.

It follows from Fig. 3 and 4 that the degree of misalignment of fiber is small for the case of small values of E_f/E_0 and l/d . This trend is more enhanced for the case of the cosine-type distribution of the fiber orientation. To see this more clearly, we have plotted the values of E_L/E_{*x} as a function of α for two types of distribution of the fiber orientation and $f = 0.2$ and 0.4 in Fig. 5

Table 2 The Values of E_{*}/E_0 ; $\nu_f = 0.17$ and $\nu_0 = 0.42$

($E_f/E_0 = 30$)

($E_f/E_0 = 100$)

1/d	$E_f/E_0 = 30$					$E_f/E_0 = 100$				
	0.1	0.2	f 0.3	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.2	f 0.3	0.4	0.5
10	2.32	3.81	5.06	7.45	9.71	2.94	5.27	8.10	11.61	16.11
30	3.38	5.86	8.44	11.13	13.94	6.66	12.88	19.75	27.39	35.93
50	3.66	6.36	9.12	11.93	14.80	8.50	16.41	24.77	33.62	43.01
100	3.83	6.67	9.53	12.40	15.29	10.02	19.23	28.61	38.19	47.97
1000	3.91	6.81	9.71	12.62	15.52	10.89	20.79	30.68	40.58	50.48

where $E_f/E_0 = 100$ and $1/d = 50$ are used. In this figure we have also plotted the results for the case of three-dimensional fiber orientation, i.e. about x_3 axis[11]. It follows from Fig. 5 that the values of E_L/E_* for the cases of two-dimensional model (present case) and the cosine-type distribution are larger than those for the cases of three-dimensional model and the uniform-type distribution, respectively.

As a summary, the values of E_L/E_0 are plotted in Fig. 6 as a function of f for various values of $1/d$ and E_f/E_0 .

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. The present analysis is based upon the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method[10] and the average induced strain approach of Taya, Chou and Mura[8,9].

2. Previous theories[1-6] of effective Young's modulus of two-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composites are performed by first evaluating the modulus of the aligned short fiber composite at the same fiber volume content. And the modulus value at a specific fiber orientation is obtained by tensor transformation of the aligned fiber case. Then the effective Young's modulus is derived by integrating the modulus values within the range of fiber orientation distributions and using the fiber orientation distribution function as the weighting function in the integration. The linear superposition of elastic moduli of different orientations neglects the interaction of the fibers, which is included in the present analysis.

3. The effects of the fiber aspect ratio, the fiber-matrix stiffness ratio, and the volume fraction of fiber on the effective Young's modulus of a two-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composite are studied for both the uniform-type and the cosine-type fiber orientation distributions.

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Fig. 3 The Effect of Aspect Ratio l/d on the Variation of the Normalized Effective Young's Modulus E_L/E_* with Fiber Distribution Limit α ; $E_f/E_0 = 100$, $\nu_f = 0.17$, $\nu_0 = 0.42$, and $\rho = \rho_0$

Fig. 4 The Effect of Young's Modulus Ratio E_f/E_0 on the Variation of E_L/E_* with α ; $\nu_f = 0.17$, $\nu_0 = 0.42$, $l/d = 50$, and $\rho = \rho_0$

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Fig. 5 The Effect of the Distribution Pattern and Volume Fraction f on the Variation of E_L/E_* with α ;

$E_f/E_0 = 100$, $\nu_f = 0.17$, $\nu_0 = 0.42$, and $l/d = 50$

Fig. 6 The Effective Young's Moduli E_L/E_0

$\nu_f = 0.17$, $\nu_0 = 0.42$,
 $\rho = \rho_0$, and $\alpha = 90^\circ$